

PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS' RESILIENCE LEVEL: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED S.T.R.I.V.E. PROGRAM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 8

Pages: 955-965

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2311

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13684064

Manuscript Accepted: 07-08-2024

Public School Teachers' Resilience Level: Basis for a Proposed S.T.R.I.V.E. Program

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Abstract

This study sought to determine the extent of resilience of 119 Grade V public-school teachers in Labangal District in the school year 2022-2023 as a basis for an intervention program. This study employed quantitative research utilizing a descriptive-survey research design. Slovin's Formula sampling design was utilized to get the desired sample of the respondents. Mean was used to analyze the data. Based on the findings of the study, among the three schools in Labangal District, the extent of teachers' resilience in terms of social skills and peer support was often manifested, which indicates a high level of teachers' resilience, while sometimes manifested in terms of spiritual influences, social skills and peer support, and personal competencies and persistence which indicate moderately high teachers' resilience. Nevertheless, teachers' resilience lies in their ability to adapt, overcome challenges, and inspire students to persevere in adversity, fostering a positive learning environment.

Keywords: *educational management, public-school teachers, teachers' resilience, descriptive survey*

Introduction

One pressing global issue is the resilience of teachers amidst mounting challenges in the education sector. Teachers face increasing demands, including adapting to new technologies, managing diverse classrooms, addressing students' socio-emotional needs, and navigating uncertain educational policies. Factors like inadequate support systems, insufficient professional development opportunities, and societal undervaluation of the teaching profession exacerbate these challenges. Building and sustaining teachers' resilience is crucial for ensuring quality education and fostering positive learning environments worldwide (Razmjoo & Ayoobian, 2019; Ratanasiripong et al., 2020; Yada et al., 2021). Teaching is terrific because teachers can change kids' lives. However, there is a need for many individuals to be aware of the difficulties associated with this line of employment. Teachers deal with various difficulties both inside and outside the classroom. These include the need to comprehend the various learning difficulties that students may be experiencing, student family issues, bullying, a lack of funding, the need to discipline students, never-ending paperwork, pressure from school administrators, and burnout (Boldrini et al., 2019; Cooper et al., 2019; Ross et al., 2020).

Hence, resilience is one of the components that should be considered in improving and formulating mental health programs in social and global practices in the 21st century. Resilient people have the fortitude to process and get through adversity. Low-resilient individuals struggle to manage stress and may resort to negative coping techniques. Resilient individuals rely on their assets and network of allies to overcome obstacles and find solutions. Building teachers' resilience level minimizes teachers' stress and burnout and improves teachers' commitment, job satisfaction, well-being, instructional quality, work enjoyment, motivation, professional identity, retention, agency, and self-efficacy (Ergün & Dewaele, 2021; Hipson et al., 2019; Scheffold, 2019).

Unfortunately, identified public teachers in Labangal District encounter several challenges in school and their personal lives, affecting their emotional aspects and teaching performance. If these problems are not fixed, they could encourage an environment of chaos and lack of discipline, creating a vicious cycle from which it is hard to break free. They may also harm students' self-esteem, morale, and academic achievement. As a public school teacher, the researcher faces numerous challenges that require resilience, such as managing large class sizes, addressing diverse students' needs, navigating bureaucratic systems, handling disciplinary issues, overcoming limited resources, and adapting to ever-changing educational policies and standards. However, more research is needed to understand the resilience levels of public school teachers. While resilience is crucial for educators, more specific studies must focus on this aspect in public school environments. Existing research tends to be broad or focused on specific groups, overlooking public school teachers' unique challenges. Addressing this gap is vital for developing targeted interventions to support teachers' well-being and improve education quality.

Researching teachers' resilience is crucial as it unveils the intricate factors underpinning teachers' burnout, elucidates pathways to enhance teachers' well-being, bolsters students' outcomes, and informs the development of effective interventions and support mechanisms vital for the sustainability and success of the education system. Understanding teachers' resilience not only addresses the pressing issue of burnout. It also fosters a more robust educational environment where educators and students thrive, ensuring education delivery continuity and efficacy.

The researcher conducted this study to determine the extent of resilience of public-school teachers in Labangal District in the school year 2022-2023. The results also determined the extent of the respondents' resilience in terms of spiritual influences, personal competencies and persistence, social skills and peer support, and family cohesion. An intervention program was also crafted to help the teachers cope with these problems.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the resilience level of public-school teachers in Labangal District in the School Year 2022-2023 as the basis for an intervention program. Specifically, it did the following:

1. To determine the extent of resilience of the public-school teachers in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 1.1. spiritual influences;
 - 1.2. personal competencies and persistence;
 - 1.3. social skills and peer support, and
 - 1.4. family cohesion.
2. To develop an intervention program based on the results of the study.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized quantitative research and a descriptive survey. A range of methods for methodically analyzing statistical or numerical data to study social phenomena is known as quantitative research design. Because of this, quantitative research is measurement-based and presupposes that the phenomena being examined can be measured. Its goals are to confirm the measurements and look for patterns and correlations in the data. Quantitative research aims to gather numerical data and extrapolate it to other demographics. With this design, every detail is well thought out and planned before any data is collected, and the researcher has a specific research question to be answered. Statistics and numbers are examples of data (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020; Habib, 2021; Rahman, 2020; Surucu & Maslacki, 2020; Swart et al., 2019).

Moreover, quantitative research design ascertains the proportion of people who hold a given belief, behavior, or emotion. Large sample sizes are standard in quantitative projects, focusing on the volume of responses rather than the more nuanced or emotional understanding that qualitative research seeks to elicit. Each respondent was typically asked the same questions in a quantitative research design, which ensured that the entire data sample could be analyzed. The data were provided in a numerical format and analyzed statistically in a quantifiable way. However, surveys can be designed to diverge if the respondent answered in a particular way (Bloomfield et al., 2021; Rahman, 2020; Sileyew, 2019).

Additionally, quantitative research design often reflects a deterministic philosophy rooted in the post-positivist paradigm or school of thought. Post-positivists study causes and how various causes interact to shape results. The post-positivist perspective embraces that reality can only be found imperfectly and probabilistically. Usually, a deductive method is used, in which most ideas or concepts are reduced to variables, and their relationships are examined. The resulting information is derived via meticulous measurement, observation, and interpretation of the natural world (Sürücü & Maslacki, 2020).

On the other hand, descriptive survey research uses quantitative and qualitative data to give accurate and pertinent information. Descriptive survey design, a quick research technique, engages the respondents, who are the focus of the study's goal. In descriptive research, more than one variable is examined. Unlike in experimental research, they cannot control the variables when they do this kind of study. Only surveys, observations, and case studies are acceptable research methods for descriptive studies. The researcher can observe, gather meaningful and trustworthy responses, and analyze the data gathered (Millner et al., 2020; Siedlecki, 2020; Story & Tait, 2019).

Furthermore, survey design methods can collect a large amount of data from a diverse audience. The survey's design aids in frequency analysis and pattern recognition of survey results. In market research, descriptive survey design is used for the following purposes: examining audiences' opinions, assessing customers' satisfaction with the company's offering, and evaluating audiences' perceptions of customer assistance (Braun et al., 2021; Siedlecki, 2020).

Survey research design is a systematic and structured approach to collect and analyze data from a sample population by administering the survey using questionnaires. The primary objective is to gather information on various topics, attitudes, opinions, or behaviors within a specific population. This design involves formulating a set of carefully crafted questions that are then distributed to a representative sample of individuals. Surveys can be conducted through various mediums, such as online platforms, telephone interviews, face-to-face interactions, or mailed questionnaires (Braun et al., 2020; Siedlecki, 2020).

The survey research design is beneficial in studying large populations and understanding the prevalence of certain attitudes, behaviors, or characteristics within that group. Researchers carefully design surveys to ensure reliability and validity, aiming to minimize bias and errors in data collection. The versatility of survey research makes it applicable in various fields, including social sciences, marketing, public health, and education, providing valuable insights into individuals' preferences, opinions, and behaviors within a given population. The success of a survey research design relies on thoughtful planning, practical questionnaire construction, and accurate data analysis to draw meaningful and generalizable conclusions about the target population (Millner et al., 2020; Story & Tait, 2019).

Respondents

The study's respondents were 120 Grade V Public School Teachers in three public schools in the Labangal District: 30 from Labangal Elementary School, 60 from Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School, and 21 from Saludin Anas Elementary School. The researcher used Slovin's formula to determine the desired sample size. Out of 170 teachers, only 120 were chosen as the study's respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Schools	Number of Respondents	
	N	n
Labangal Elementary School	42	30
Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School	98	69
Saludin Anas Elementary School	30	21
TOTAL	170	120

The researcher established specific inclusion criteria for selecting the respondents, irrespective of gender, religion, or ethnicity. The focus was on individuals aged 25-40 who served as public school teachers at Labangal Elementary School, Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School, or Saludin Anas Elementary School. Conversely, certain groups, such as public school teachers aged 24 and below or 41 and above, were excluded from participation, as were those unwilling or unable to provide consent or cooperate during the data collection.

The respondents have the right to withdraw from the study at any point, with assurances that their decision would not adversely affect their relationship with the school or program. Additionally, measures were in place to address any discomfort, distress, or emotional unease experienced by the respondents during the study, ensuring their well-being remained a priority throughout the research process. They were assured that they could opt out of the study at any juncture without fear of negative repercussions on their standing with the school or program.

This guarantee was extended to safeguard the autonomy and comfort of the respondents, fostering an environment of trust and respect. Furthermore, proactive measures were implemented to promptly address any discomfort, distress, or emotional unease the respondents encountered during their involvement in the study. This commitment to prioritizing their well-being underscored the researcher's ethical responsibility and ensured that the research process remained ethical and humane.

Instruments

Only one instrument was used in this study: a questionnaire about the resilience level of public school teachers. It was adapted from the study of Platsidou and Daniilidou (2022), "Teachers' Resilience Scale: An Integrated Instrument for Assessing Protective Factors of Teachers' Resilience. It has four indicators: spiritual influences, personal competencies and persistence, social skills and peer support, and family cohesion. Spiritual influences comprise three statements; personal competencies and persistence comprise nine statements; social skills and peer support comprise seven, and family cohesion comprise seven.

Table 2. *Cronbach's Alpha Internal Consistency*

Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

The retest method was administered to 3 public schools in Labangal District: Labangal Elementary School, Saavedra Saway Central Elementary School, and Saludin Anas Elementary School.

The results showed that Cronbach's alpha was excellent for internal consistency: $\alpha = .900$. The researcher can trust that the survey questions were reliable.

Table 3. *Reliability Statistics*

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
.901	.8800	25

Procedure

The researcher collected the data based on the book of Elsayed and Elsayed (2021) entitled "Research Design, Methodology, and Data Collection." The researcher followed the following steps. First, decide what needs to be collected. Second, decide how long the data collection will take. Third, the data collection strategy must be decided. Fourth, gather the data, follow, analyze the data, and then formulate the conclusions. Before taking these actions, the researcher obtained a letter of permission from the General Santos City Schools Division Office, which was signed and approved after being reviewed by the adviser. The received copy was delivered to the administrators of the schools where the surveys were done (Elsayed & Elsayed, 2021).

First, the researcher made a research questionnaire and asked the expert validators to validate the instrument. Second, the researcher asked permission from the Ethics and Review Committee of the Graduate School. Upon the approval of the request, the researcher asked permission to conduct the study from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent, Schools Division Office of the Division of General Santos City. Fourth, the researcher prepared for the reproduction according to the number of the target respondents. After reproducing the questionnaires, the researcher personally explained the Informed Consent Form (I.C.F.) and administered the questionnaire to the respondents. They were given ample time to complete the questionnaires. Sixth, while retrieving the questionnaires, the researcher checked if the respondents had accomplished all the items. Finally, the completed questionnaires were summarized, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

Data Analysis

Mean. This tool was utilized to determine the resilience level of public school teachers and address research objective 1.

Ethical Considerations

Significant ethical issues play a vital role in gathering the data. The ethical considerations in this research were concerned with the proper conduct of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. The R.M.M.C. Ethics and Review Committee's requirements for ethical consideration were adhered to in this study, especially when dealing with the respondents and the data, including but not limited to the following:

Voluntary Participation. The respondents were free to participate without fear of consequences, loss of benefits, or compensation plans. Following an explanation of the study's purpose, the respondent's right to add to the body of knowledge was duly considered and expected. The respondents in this study were not coerced into taking part. If they get uncomfortable while participating in the study, they can stop.

Privacy and confidentiality. Respondents' privacy rights were not violated without their informed agreement under the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards this fundamental human right. Allowing the respondents to omit their names from the survey questionnaire was one of the techniques to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. In addition, confidentiality and privacy were preserved by withholding the informants' personal information, such as their age, gender, occupation, and health conditions. As a result, their identity was kept private for security reasons. Their answers to the survey questionnaire were kept confidential and treated as such.

Informed consent process. Given the limitations of the inquiry, potential research volunteers were fully informed of the study's goals, methods, and rewards in the most detailed way conceivable. The fact that the respondents' permission was requested demonstrates that their participation was freely given. It gave the respondents the necessary information and discussed the survey's methodology. The informed consent form required the respondents to sign to indicate that they freely chose to participate in the study. The respondents' identities were not listed in the survey form, and their responses were kept private. The respondents knew they could withdraw from participating in the study anytime.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. To facilitate additional inferences and enable the respondents to grasp the study's substance, the researcher explained the study's goal. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the relevance and reason for the study.

Risks. Research was conducted to determine if there was an acceptable positive benefit-risk ratio. This study's need to protect the respondents from significant harm is equally essential. The study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the respondents were not harmed since their identity was held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. The researcher ensured the respondents were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. In answering the survey questionnaire, the researcher ensured the respondents did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. The importance of teacher resilience on a global scale cannot be emphasized enough, as it significantly impacts the advancement of societies worldwide, particularly in ensuring quality education. This study holds immense relevance for the education sector, providing valuable insights that can aid the Department of Education and district supervisors in developing effective strategies to reduce the heightened stress levels experienced by teachers and respond to challenges posed by events like the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, the findings from this research offer valuable guidance to school leaders in shaping future adjustments to educational policies, curricula, and strategies aimed at supporting teachers in effectively carrying out their duties and ultimately enhancing the

quality of education provided.

Furthermore, teachers could reassess themselves in conveying the pedagogical domains as confident, knowledgeable, and prepared to the learners. As such, knowing their resilience level becomes highly relevant to understanding what influences their belief in their ability to successfully cope with the tasks, obligations, and challenges related to their role as teachers. This study served as a reference for other related studies, and they may be able to use the findings in further research similar to this study.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the research had misinterpreted someone else's work. Grammarly software and other plagiarism checkers were used in the study. Integrity and good character, linked to moral principles and ideals, are needed to function as a researcher. The researcher must know more about plagiarism to produce a respectable research report.

Fabrication. The report showed no evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. The investigator utilized and incorporated ideas associated with the data and other inferential notions.

Falsification. There was no indication that the study overstated or exaggerated anything or deliberately falsified the data to meet a model or theoretical assumption. Additionally, this study needed to follow data manipulation practices, which include making claims based on incomplete information or omitting crucial elements and using materials, instruments, or procedures that might mislead others.

Conflict of Interest (C.O.I.). There were no signs of a conflict of interest in the study, including the disclosure of a conflict of interest (C.O.I.), which is a collection of situations where a professional's assessment of a primary interest—such as the well-being of the respondents or the reliability of the research—is likely to be impacted by a secondary interest—such as financial or academic rewards. Moreover, the respondents are not coerced into surveying by the researcher; instead, she has no power or influence over them.

Deceit. The study did not mislead the respondents about any possible danger. Since the respondents have completed higher education, their rights must be enormously safeguarded in any study. Therefore, reasonable and acceptable guidelines must be followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The researcher in this study adhered to established protocols by obtaining approval from the panelists, adviser, and the RMMC ERC committee. Following this, formal letters seeking approval were sent to the school division Superintendents. Subsequently, another letter, including the endorsed letter from the school division Superintendent, was addressed to the district supervisor and principal of the involved schools. Before administering the survey questionnaire, the Grade Five teachers participating underwent orientation.

Authorship. Ethical authorship involves recognizing and acknowledging individuals who significantly contributed to the research, ensuring that only those meeting the authorship criteria are included. The researcher ensures that the study's results transparently represent all parties' contributions, maintaining fairness and credibility in research outputs. Adherence to ethical authoring norms is emphasized to ensure a transparent and fair contribution to the advancement of knowledge.

Results and Discussion

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the study's data are covered in this chapter.

The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Spiritual Influences

Table 4. *The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Spiritual Influences*

Spiritual Influences	Mean	Description
1. Sometimes fate or God can help them overcome their challenges	3.4	Sometimes
2. Sometimes, they believe things happen for a reason	3.1	Sometimes
3. Sometimes, they have to act on a hunch	3.6	Often
TOTAL	3.4	Sometimes

Table 4 presents the extent of resilience of the respondents in terms of spiritual influences. Mean and description were utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data showed that the extent of teachers' resilience was occasionally manifested in connection with spiritual influences, which garnered a mean of 3.4. It implies that teachers believe that either fate or a higher power, like God, has the potential to assist in overcoming challenges or difficulties. Teachers sometimes believed that fate in God helped them overcome challenges \bar{x} (3.4). They sometimes believed everything happens for a reason \bar{x} (3.1). They sometimes act on a hunch \bar{x} (3.6).

The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence

Table 5 presents the extent of resilience of the respondents in terms of personal competencies and persistence. Mean and description

were utilized to treat the data gathered.

Table 5. *The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence*

Personal Competencies and Persistence	Mean	Description
1. They can adapt to change	2.9	Sometimes
2. Under pressure, they can focus and think clearly	2.9	Sometimes
3. They prefer to take the lead in problem-solving	2.6	Sometimes
4. They are not easily discouraged by failure	2.8	Sometimes
5. They think of someone as a strong person	3.5	Often
6. If necessary, they can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect other people	3.2	Sometimes
7. They can handle unpleasant feelings, such as anger or fear	3.1	Sometimes
8. They like challenges	3.2	Sometimes
9. They work hard to attain their goals	2.9	Sometimes
TOTAL	3.0	Sometimes

Data revealed that the extent of teachers' resilience was manifested occasionally in terms of personal competence and persistence, which garnered a mean of 3.0, which implies that teachers occasionally observe multiple aspects, including adaptability to change, maintaining focus and clear thinking under pressure, a proactive approach to problem-solving, resilience against discouragement from failure, self-perception as a strong individual, willingness to make challenging decisions affecting others, capability to handle unpleasant emotions like anger or fear, eagerness to embrace challenges, and a dedicated work ethic towards achieving personal goals. Teachers were sometimes adaptive to changes \bar{x} (2.9). They could focus sometimes and think clearly despite pressure \bar{x} (2.9). Teachers sometimes preferred to be leaders \bar{x} (2.6). They sometimes do not get discouraged easily \bar{x} (2.8). They were often strong \bar{x} (3.5). Teachers make difficult decisions sometimes \bar{x} (3.2). They can manage anger and fear sometimes \bar{x} (3.1). Teachers sometimes like challenges \bar{x} (3.2). Teachers work hard sometimes for their goals \bar{x} (2.9).

The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Social Skills and Peer Support

Table 6 presents the extent of the respondents' resilience in terms of social skills and peer support. Mean and description were utilized to treat the data gathered.

Table 6. *The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Social Skills and Peer Support*

Social Skills and Peer Support	Mean	Description
1. In their workplace, they enjoy being together with other people	3.4	Sometimes
2. New friendships are something I make quickly in the workplace	3.6	Often
3. Meeting new people in their workplace is something they are good at	3.7	Often
4. In their workplace, When they are with others, they easily laugh	3.8	Often
5. They can discuss personal issues with their peers	3.5	Often
6. The bonds between their peers and they are strong	3.7	Often
7. They get support from their peers	3.5	Often
TOTAL	3.6	Often

Data revealed that the extent of teacher's resilience in terms of social skills and peer support was manifested most of the time, garnering a mean of 3.6. It suggests a frequent and notable demonstration of resilience in interpersonal relationships and the utilization of peer support within the teaching community. Teachers sometimes enjoy being with other people \bar{x} (3.4). They often made new friend quickly in their workplace \bar{x} (3.6). They were often good at meeting new people \bar{x} (3.7). Teachers often laugh when they are with others \bar{x} (3.8). They often discuss personal issues with colleagues \bar{x} (3.5). They often establish strong bonds with peers \bar{x} (3.7). They often receive peer support \bar{x} (3.5).

The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Family Cohesion

Table 7 presents the extent of the respondents' resilience in terms of family cohesion. Mean and description were utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that the extent of teachers' resilience in connection with family cohesion, which garnered a mean of 3.1, was manifested occasionally, indicating intermittent instances where their resilience was demonstrated in maintaining familial unity and stability. Teachers and their families have a common understanding of life, sometimes \bar{x} (3.2). They sometimes felt happy with their families \bar{x} (2.9). Their families are sometimes having healthy coherence \bar{x} (2.9). Moreover, their family keeps a positive outlook sometimes despite challenges \bar{x} (2.9). Teachers and their families were often loyal to each other \bar{x} (3.5). They do things together sometimes \bar{x} (3.2). Finally, their family was sometimes there for them \bar{x} (3.1).

Table 7. *The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Family Cohesion*

Family Cohesion	Mean	Description
1. Their family's understanding of what is essential in life is very similar to them	3.2	Sometimes
2. They feel thrilled with their family	2.9	Sometimes
3. Their family is characterized by healthy coherence	2.9	Sometimes
4. under challenging periods, their family keeps a positive outlook on the future	2.8	Sometimes
5. Facing other people, our family acts loyal towards one another	3.5	Often
6. In their family, we like to do things together	3.2	Sometimes
7. When needed, they always have someone in their workplace who can help them	3.1	Sometimes
TOTAL	3.1	Sometimes

The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Spiritual Influences

The extent of the teacher's resilience was manifested occasionally in terms of spiritual influences. According to Ainsworth and Oldfield (2019), resilience is the process and outcome of successfully responding to unfavorable or difficult life situations. It is the ability to adapt mentally, emotionally, and behaviorally to one's circumstances and those around them. It is crucial to remember that developing their skill set to become resilient over time is necessary. One must try to develop resilience and encounter obstacles along the way. It depends on internal factors, such as communication and self-esteem, and external factors, like social support and resources available. Even resilient people go through stress, emotional turmoil, and pain. Working through emotional pain and suffering is a sign of resilience.

Moreover, spiritual practices, such as meditation, prayer, or reflection, can be invaluable tools for teachers to cultivate self-care, manage stress, and maintain emotional well-being. These practices help teachers cultivate mindfulness, presence, and inner calm, allowing them to approach challenges with clarity, compassion, and resilience. By nurturing their spiritual well-being, teachers can replenish their energy, maintain a positive mindset, and continue to show up as their best selves for their students. Spirituality also promotes a sense of community and support among teachers. Engaging in spiritual activities or joining like-minded communities can create opportunities for teachers to share experiences, find solace in collective wisdom, and draw strength from the support of others (Brown et al., 2020; Chesak et al., 2019; Riehm et al., 2021).

The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence

The extent of the teacher's resilience was manifested occasionally in personal competencies and persistence. In the study of Hipson et al. (2019), resilience is the capacity to handle complex, upsetting, or challenging life situations in a way that gives the individual more coping mechanisms than before the event that caused the disruption. These include mental traits, including a propensity for planning, self-evaluation to determine what has worked, a sense of agency or drive to deal with difficulties, and self-assurance in one's ability to do so successfully. Teacher resilience has been "conceptualized as a capacity, a process, and an end" precisely.

Furthermore, the ability to relate meaningfully with people is called social competence. It is a critical talent that interventions can shape. Furthermore, it is described as the ability to handle social relationships properly. Social competence is establishing and sustaining close relationships, getting along with people, and acting appropriately in social settings. Considering the complexity of interpersonal relationships, social competence results from various cognitive abilities, emotional intelligence, behavioral skills, social awareness, and cultural and personal values about interpersonal relationships. To elucidate this notion, social competency is influenced by developmental traits, the specific social setting, and cultural characteristics (Chesak et al., 2019; Hipson et al., 2019; Junge et al., 2020).

The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Social Skills and Peer Support

The extent of the teacher's resilience manifested mostly in terms of social skills and peer support. As Ainsworth and Oldfield (2019) stated, resilience is the ability to quickly heal and recover from diseases, psychological issues, negative experiences, or stress. In other words, resilience is a person's ability to overcome adversity and adapt to new situations successfully; it is a person's ability to recover, focus on success, and continue his purpose to achieve success when faced with difficulties and problems. The characteristics and protective mechanisms allow adaptation to danger, threats, and challenges. Resistance to stressful situations and events is facilitated

by psychological resilience. Individuals with high resilience have a higher stress threshold and thus perform better in stressful situations such as conflict, crisis, and change.

Additionally, people feel powerful because they regain self-discipline and aim for their goals. They develop momentum and energy because they feel the purpose, direction, and strength. One might feel more alive as they grow more motivated. Having structure and order in their life allows them to relax more since they know they often influence their time. Structures, however, are necessary to embody statutory, geographical, and organizational conditions. A system that specifies how certain activities are directed to achieve an organization's goals is called an organizational structure (Kangas-Dick & O'Shaughnessy, 2020; Mansfield, 2020; Razmjoo & Ayoobiyan, 2019).

The Extent of Resilience of the Respondents in terms of Family Cohesion

Data disclosed that family cohesion garnered a mean of 3.1, described as sometimes. It means that the extent of the teacher's resilience was occasionally manifested.

Based on Cooper et al. (2019), improving resilience can help middle school students reduce the adverse effects of stress and improve their ability to adjust to their surroundings. Given the importance of resilience in a person's life, what steps can educators take to strengthen students' resilience? Prior experience, relationships with parents and peers, personality, and environment could all impact a student's resilience. These factors can be divided into individual characteristics, social environment, and family level. Educators can help students' resilience by enhancing their positive characteristics, improving the study environment, and creating a warm family atmosphere.

Additionally, in every educational setting, taking care of teachers' mental health and inner moods is crucial since they bring their feelings, emotions, and values to the classroom. However, in reality, teaching faces various difficulties that lead to teacher attrition, demotivation, stress, and burnout—particularly in the first five years, referred to as "the vulnerable phase," when 40–50% of instructors leave their positions. High workloads, a lack of resources for support, aversion to difficulty, poor time management, and ignorance of how to manage students' behavior and meet their needs can all contribute to this (Fernandes et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021; Mathur & Jain, 2021).

However, teaching faces many difficulties and obstacles that lead to teacher attrition, demotivation, stress, and burnout, particularly in the first five years, referred to as "the vulnerable phase." It is when 40–50% of teachers leave their positions. It could occur as a result of a heavy workload, insufficient resources for support, apprehension about difficulties, poor time management, and a lack of understanding of how to manage students' behavior and meet their needs (Garcia-Crepeo et al., 2021; Mrstik et al., 2019; Padios et al., 2022).

Conclusions

The following conclusions were established based on the data gathered:

First, data revealed that the extent of resilience in terms of spiritual influences was manifested occasionally. Second, the extent of resilience regarding personal competence and persistence was manifested occasionally. Third, the extent of resilience in terms of social skills and peer support was manifested most of the time. Lastly, the extent of resilience in terms of family cohesion was manifested occasionally. Resilience is generally demonstrated occasionally across various dimensions, including spiritual influences, personal competence, persistence, and family cohesion. However, social skills and peer support are areas where resilience is more frequently exhibited. While individuals may have intermittent resilience in several areas, they consistently rely on their social networks for support.

The following recommendations below were The study's results and findings provide the basis for the following suggestions:

For the spiritual influences, the education sector may encourage supportive communities where teachers can share spiritual beliefs and experiences, fostering meaning-making by connecting teaching to broader spiritual or moral principles and cultivating gratitude practices to enhance resilience further.

Furthermore, for social skills and peer support, the Department of Education may promote a culture of teamwork and collective problem-solving within schools, where teachers can lean on each other during challenging times. To promote positive interpersonal dynamics, offer conflict resolution and constructive criticism training.

Moreover, for family cohesion, the education sector may provide resources and workshops on effective communication and boundary-setting strategies, empowering educators to navigate the demands of their profession while maintaining strong family relationships.

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